

Report of the webinar sessions “Refining the Global Strategic Research Agenda (SRA)”

Table of Contents

1.1	List of participants _____	3
1.2	Welcome _____	5
1.2.1	Welcome & Introduction _____	5
1.3	Update on the SRA _____	6
1.3.1	Update on the Progress of the SRA _____	6
1.4	Presenting SRA 2.0 _____	8
1.4.1	SRA 2.0: Implementing Your Feedback _____	8
1.4.2	SRA 2.0: Novelties _____	8
1.4.3	SRA 2.0: To Be Discussed _____	9
1.5	Discussion & Feedback on SRA 2.0 _____	10
1.5.1	Question 1: How clear is the overall purpose of the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) as described in the draft? _____	10
1.5.2	Question 2: Do you think the SRA addresses the right level of ambition for global plant health research coordination? _____	13
1.5.3	Question 3: Is it clear how the SRA relates to the IPPC framework, and that the SRA has been developed independently rather than as a direct reflection of the IPPC? _____	14
1.5.4	Question 4: The SRA is intended to cover medium-term (5-10 years) research priorities. How should the duration of the SRA be assessed and by whom? _____	15
1.5.5	Question 5: How suitable and consistent did you find the terminology used throughout the draft SRA? _____	17
1.5.6	Question 6: To what extent does the current scope meet your expectations? _____	19
1.5.7	Question 7: Is the overall document consistently framed around this scope? _____	21
1.5.8	Question 8: Which of the following subjects do you feel should be considered and/ or explicitly stated within the scope of the SRA? _____	23
1.5.9	Question 9: How appropriate do you find the current set of objectives in the SRA? _____	25
1.5.10	Question 10: Is it clear how objectives under Research Themes and Ambitions are expected to translate into future Euphresco research calls? _____	28
1.5.11	Question 11: Underneath each objective, the Champions whose inputs were used to establish that objective are listed. How should these references to the “support” of objectives be handled in the SRA? _____	29
1.5.12	Question 12: Which objectives do you link to which cross-cutting considerations? _____	31
1.6	Future Development of the SRA _____	32

Date: 15/06/2026 (9:30 to 12:30 CEST) & 17/06/2026 (21:00 to 00:00 CEST)

Modality: remote (Teams)

Facilitators: Samantha De Gottal, Lena Vlamincx, Ria Nouwen (FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment, BE), Jassmine Zorrilla (Euphresco Network Office, Int.)

This document reports on the contents of both sessions of the webinar “Refining the Global Strategic Research Agenda”. As both sessions were identical, the contents of the presentations are only summarized once. The input on the questionnaire and open discussion is collectively reported below.

The proposed agenda was followed during the meeting and can be found below.

AGENDA

0:00	Welcome (15 min)	
0:00	Welcome & Introduction	Samantha De Gottal (FPS)
0:15	Update on the SRA (20 min)	
0:15	Update on the Progress of the SRA	Samantha De Gottal (FPS)
0:35	Presenting SRA 2.0 (45 min)	
0:35	SRA 2.0: Implementing Your Feedback	Samantha De Gottal (FPS)
1:00	SRA 2.0: Novelities	Samantha De Gottal (FPS)
1:15	SRA 2.0: To Be Discussed	Samantha De Gottal (FPS)
1:20	Break	
1:35	Discussion & Feedback on SRA 2.0 (75 min)	
1:35	Live Input on Questionnaire + Open Discussion	Lena Vlamincx & Samantha De Gottal (FPS)
2:50	Next steps (10 min)	
2:50	Future Development of the SRA	Samantha De Gottal (FPS)
3:00	End	

1.1 List of participants

Session 1 - 15/06/2026 (9:30 to 12:30 CEST)

Name	Affiliation
Anthoine Géraldine	Direction régionale de l'alimentation, de l'agriculture et de la forêt (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR)
Čipinytė Vilma	The State Plant Service under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania (VATZUM, LT)
Cruz Leonor	Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária (INIAV, PT)
De Gottal Samantha	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)
De Jonghe Kris	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO, BE)
Donghia Anna Maria	International Center for Advanced Mediterranean Agronomic Studies (CIHEAM-Bari, Int.)
Gentit Pascal	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES, FR)
Gundelach Rannes Christine	Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark (MFAFD, DK)
Gunter Joanna	Main Inspectorate of Plant Health and Seed Inspection (MIPHSI, PL)
Hietala Ari	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO, NO)
Jacobs Chris	Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA, UK)
Kaiser Marco	Bioreba (Bioreba, CH)
Lucrezia Trovato	Ministero dell'agricoltura, della sovranità alimentare e delle foreste (MASAF, IT)
Markellou Emilia	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI, GR)
Munaut Françoise	European Commission Directorate-General for Health & Food Safety (DG SANTE, Int.)
Nouwen Ria	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)
Pupelienė Silvija	The State Plant Service under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania (VATZUM, LT)
Reignault Philippe	Ministère de l'Agriculture, de l'Agro-Alimentaire et de la Souveraineté Alimentaire (MAASA, FR)
Slootbeek Annemiek	Netherlands Food and Consumer Products Safety Authority (NVWA, NL)
Topitschnig Christina	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES, AT)
Zorrilla Fontanesi Jassmine	Euphresco Network Office (ENO, Int.)

Apologies: Pauline Musschoot (FPS Health, BE)

Session 2 - 17/06/2026 (21:00 to 00:00 CEST)

Name	Affiliation
Aveskamp Maikel	Netherlands Food and Consumer Products Safety Authority (NVWA, NL)
Balan Rebijith	Ministry for Primary Industries (MPI, NZ)

Braeken Kristien	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)
Day Brittany	Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA, CA)
De Gottal Samantha	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)
Iovinella Immacolata	Council for Agronomic Research and Bioeconomy (CREA-DC, IT)
Magdolenová Marta	Chief Plant Health Officer for the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (CPHO, SK)
McGaw Annelies	Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Forestry (DAFF, AU)
Nam Kiwoong	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE, FR)
Nouwen Ria	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)
Oronje MaryLucy	Centre for Agriculture and Biosciences International (CABI, Int.)
Stephanie O'Connor Ramona	The Pacific Community (SPC, Int.)
Teulon David	Plant and Food Research (PFR, NZ)
Vlaminck Lena	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)
Zorrilla Fontanesi Jassmine	Euphresco Network Office (ENO, Int.)

Apologies: Pablo Gomez Grande (INIA-CSIC, ES)

1.2 Welcome

1.2.1 Welcome & Introduction – Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) opened the session by welcoming all participants to the webinar dedicated to refining the Global Strategic Research Agenda (SRA). She informed participants that the session was the second webinar series organized by FPS Health and the Euphresco Network Office (ENO), following earlier sessions held in January that focused on the initial development of the SRA. She clarified that, like the first webinar series, two identical sessions will be organized on 15 June and 17 June 2026 to ensure broader participation across time zones. She also noted that, although the presentations are identical, the discussions will vary depending on participants. Attendees were thus encouraged to attend both sessions if possible and to invite colleagues. Ms. De Gottal further informed attendees that the session was being recorded to be shared with all recipients of an official invitation after the webinars had concluded, alongside an extensive report of both sessions and the slides which were presented.

Ms. De Gottal then introduced the organizers of the webinar, namely the ENO and FPS Health Belgium. She presented the overall structure of the session and outlined the agenda, which included a general introduction to the Euphresco-network, EUPHRESKO III (EIII)-project and the SRA, a detailed update on its development, a presentation of the latest draft (SRA 2.0), and an open discussion based on a questionnaire that had been distributed prior to the webinar. She explained that participants would have the opportunity to ask questions after each presentation and to provide feedback during the discussion through both interactive polls and open discussion.

Ms. De Gottal provided a detailed overview of the Euphresco-network, explaining that it is a coordination platform for plant health research involving a wide range of stakeholders, including regulators, funders, research institutes, and industry actors. She described how the network supports prioritization, funding, execution and application of plant health research, and emphasized its role in facilitating knowledge exchange and coordination between stakeholders at different levels.

She further explained that the EIII-project represents an extension of this coordination at the global level, bringing together an international consortium of 35 partners covering multiple regions and disciplines within plant health. These partners include regulators, research program managers, research providers from both public and private sectors, and representatives from key industries such as forest and tree health and biotechnology, diagnostics and seed industries. Ms. De Gottal highlighted the role of “Champions”, who are partners who represent specific regions or disciplines within the EIII-project and thus played a central role in the consultation process feeding into the SRA.

Ms. De Gottal then introduced the SRA as a strategic planning document intended to define research priorities, identify knowledge gaps, and guide future research activities in plant health. She stressed that the SRA is not a unilateral initiative but a collaborative effort involving EIII partners, Euphresco-network members, and advisory organizations, including international bodies. The objective of this approach is to build a shared vision for global plant health research coordination and to support future collaboration and joint programming activities.

1.3 Update on the SRA

1.3.1 Update on the Progress of the SRA – Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) provided an extensive update on the development process of the SRA, beginning with an explanation of the adjusted project timeline. She indicated that the timeline had been revised due to both the extension of the EIII-project and the faster-than-anticipated progress in drafting the earlier versions of the document. This adjustment created additional time for consultation and refinement, ultimately allowing for a more thorough development process and improving the overall quality and robustness of the subsequent drafts.

She then proceeded to describe the initial stakeholder consultations carried out in 2025, prior to the formal drafting of the document. These consultations were coordinated by regional and disciplinary “Champions”, who engaged with a broad range of plant health stakeholders, including researchers, policy makers, funders and industry representatives. Ms. De Gottal explained that, for most regions and disciplines, the consultation process combined bottom-up input from stakeholders with top-down perspectives from key decision-makers. This approach resulted in enriched consultation reports, which formed a solid foundation for the development of the SRA. Ms. De Gottal further explained that these consultation reports were subsequently analysed and discussed during a series of bilateral meetings involving the “Champions”, the Euphresco Network Office (ENO) and FPS Health Belgium. These meetings were structured as guided discussions, allowing participants not only to review the findings of the consultation reports in more depth, but also to incorporate additional insights from ongoing consultation activities that had taken place after the reports had been submitted. In this way, the bilateral meetings provided an opportunity to validate, refine, and complement the initial stakeholder input.

Continuing her presentation, Ms. De Gottal outlined the first concrete steps taken to initiate the development of the SRA. She referred to a kick-off meeting with the “Champions” and to the Governing Board meeting of the Euphresco-network held in September 2025. She also noted that initial discussions on how to structure the development process had already taken place earlier, during the General Assembly (GA) of the EIII-project in April 2025. During this meeting, it was agreed that the development of the SRA should follow an iterative approach, whereby successive draft versions would be developed based on stakeholder input and subsequently presented to EIII partners, Euphresco-network members, and Advisory Board members for review and feedback. This iterative cycle of drafting and consultation was intended to gradually lead to a well-developed and broadly supported final document. Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) further highlighted several key outcomes of the April 2025 GA discussions. These included the agreement on a preliminary structure for the SRA, consisting of an introduction, a scope section, and sections outlining research priorities and objectives. In addition, a dual-layer approach was proposed, whereby the SRA would consist of a fixed component alongside a more dynamic element capable of adapting to emerging plant health challenges. The importance of including both regional and global research priorities was also emphasised, as well as the need to link research objectives to key focus areas such as trade, plant production and productivity, and environmental considerations. She added that the subsequent kick-off meeting provided further input to guide the development process. Participants stressed the importance of clearly highlighting the link between the SRA and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. Furthermore, the idea was introduced to begin the drafting process with a concise “one-pager”, which would serve as an initial

conceptual framework for the SRA. This one-pager was later presented at the 2025 Governing Board meeting, where it provided a visual overview of the proposed structure of the SRA and reflected the key elements that had emerged from both the GA discussions and the Champions' meeting.

Ms. De Gottal then explained how these initial steps led to the development of the first written draft of the SRA (SRA 0.1) in December 2025. This draft included preliminary versions of the introduction and scope sections, as well as a glossary and a set of provisional research themes. She noted that the glossary had been added in response to repeated feedback from the bilateral meetings, where the importance of clear terminology and well-defined concepts had been strongly emphasised. The provisional themes were derived from an initial analysis of the consultation reports, combined with insights gathered during the bilateral discussions. In total, 12 themes were identified, providing an initial overview of the main thematic areas to be addressed in the SRA. This draft was subsequently presented during the first webinar series in January in order to collect feedback from a wider group of stakeholders.

Ms. De Gottal continued with a detailed explanation of the development of SRA 1.0, which represented the first full (almost) draft of the document. She indicated that this version incorporated several changes in response to the feedback received on SRA 0.1. While relatively minor revisions were made to the glossary and introductory sections, more substantial changes were introduced regarding the scope and overall structure of the document. To improve clarity, additional definitions were included in the glossary, and an explanatory paragraph was added to the introduction to better define the scope of the SRA. The relationship between the SRA and international regulatory bodies such as the IPPC was also further clarified within the scope section, emphasising the independent nature of the SRA development process. In addition, Ms. De Gottal explained that the 12 provisional themes presented in SRA 0.1 were significantly restructured in SRA 1.0 into 3 short-term research themes and 3 long-term aims. Alongside this restructuring, the development of provisional research objectives was introduced as a key new element of the document. Returning to the original consultation reports, a total of 761 research priorities were identified across the nine regions and four disciplines covered by the project. These were further enriched with insights from the bilateral meetings, resulting in an additional ten priorities and bringing the total to 771. She explained that these priorities were analysed and clustered through a combination of AI-assisted methods and expert review. This process ultimately led to the formulation of a structured set of 30 objectives. Ms. De Gottal noted that SRA 1.0 was presented at the 2026 GA, providing another opportunity for discussion and feedback. In addition, all EIII partners, Euphresco-network members and Advisory Board members were invited to submit written feedback on the draft.

Finally, Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) explained that this written feedback and input from the GA formed the basis for the development of the most recent draft, SRA 2.0, which would be presented in detail in the subsequent part of the webinar.

1.4 Presenting SRA 2.0

1.4.1 SRA 2.0: Implementing Your Feedback – Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)

Ms. De Gottal presented the latest draft of the SRA (SRA 2.0), focusing on the main changes introduced following the feedback received on SRA 1.0. She explained that two key issues had been repeatedly identified during the previous consultation rounds. The first concern related to a lack of clarity regarding the scope of the document, in particular the distinction between “phytosanitary” and “plant health” research. The second concern related to uncertainty surrounding the role of the EIII-project and the SRA, particularly in relation to the IPPC.

To address the first issue, Ms. De Gottal explained that the definitions of both phytosanitary and plant health research had been revised and clarified in the updated draft. In SRA 2.0, phytosanitary research is defined as focusing on regulated pests, whereas plant health research encompasses both regulated pests and non-regulated new and emerging pests. She clarified that the SRA adopts this broader plant health perspective, explicitly limiting the scope to regulated pests and new and/ or emerging non-regulated pests.

Beyond updating the glossary, Ms. De Gottal explained that the explanatory paragraph on the scope, which had been introduced in SRA 1.0, had been completely rewritten. This revised paragraph more clearly describes the scope of the document and highlights that it remains consistent with that of the previous Euphresco-network SRA published in 2017. She emphasised that the main difference lies in the interpretation of this scope, as the current SRA is developed within a broader global context. Furthermore, the paragraph clarifies the use of the term “plant health”, noting that it is consistent with terminology used by the IPPC, while also indicating that the definition has been adapted to better fit the needs of the SRA.

Ms. De Gottal then addressed the second major concern regarding the role of EIII and the SRA. She explained that this role had not been sufficiently clear in the previous version and that certain elements, particularly within the “Ambitions” (formerly referred to as “Aims”), appeared to overlap with the mandate of the IPPC. To address this, the Ambitions were thoroughly revised in SRA 2.0. These revisions were intended to avoid any suggestion that EIII or the future global network would be directly involved in regulatory or standard-setting activities. In addition, Ms. De Gottal explained that further clarification had been added to the scope section to better explain the relationship between the Ambitions and the Research Themes. She highlighted that the Ambitions represent broader, long-term goals, which are not intended to be directly achieved by EIII or the future global network. Instead, the research activities carried out via the network are expected to contribute indirectly to these Ambitions. In this way, the outcomes of the Research Themes will underpin and support the achievement of the Ambitions.

Ms. De Gottal also presented several smaller changes introduced in SRA 2.0. These included further improvements in terminology and phrasing throughout the document, refinement of certain objectives, and a restructuring of sections to enhance overall clarity and coherence.

1.4.2 SRA 2.0: Novelties – Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) finalized her presentation by discussing the new additions to the current draft. Certain sections were expanded, being the sections on the development and

on the evaluation and adaptation process of the SRA. New elements were also introduced, including a concise summary of the objectives and an acknowledgement section. Finally, Ms. De Gottal presented a revised visual representation of the SRA, based on the initial one-pager made at the very start of the document's development. In this representation, Research Themes are depicted as clusters of branches, objectives as leaves, and the Ambitions as baskets collecting the fruits (the outcomes) of the tree. She explained that this metaphor is intended to illustrate how the outcomes generated through the Research Themes ultimately contribute to and support the higher-level Ambitions of the SRA.

1.4.3 SRA 2.0: To Be Discussed – Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)

To conclude, Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) gave a brief overview of the points to be discussed after the break.

1.5 Discussion & Feedback on SRA 2.0 – Samantha De Gottal, Ria Nouwen & Lena Vlaminck (FPS Health, BE)

The discussion was based on the questionnaire which had been sent to all participants alongside the official invitation for the webinar sessions. Based on these questions, participants completed a series of polls addressing the general purpose and ambition of the SRA, clarity of the scope, terminology and phrasing, as well as the coverage of the SRA and the structure of the objectives. Unless stated otherwise, participants were only able to select one answer for each poll. After all polls were completed, an open discussion followed, moderated by Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) in the first session and Ms. Vlaminck (FPS Health, BE) in the second session where the results of each poll were discussed. Participants had the opportunity to ask questions, express opinions and provide feedback on each of the poll questions. These deeper insights will be considered for the further improvement of SRA 2.0.

1.5.1 Question 1: How clear is the overall purpose of the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) as described in the draft?

Results summary: 50.0% of participants indicated the purpose of the SRA was clear, 45.8% said it was very clear, and 4.2% found it somewhat unclear.

Session 1:

Mr. Jacobs (DEFRA, UK) initiated the discussion by explaining that, although he considered the purpose of the SRA to be generally clear, he remained uncertain about how the document fits within the global system of research coordination, particularly the SRA's relation to the IPPC. He highlighted that the SRA is largely based on contributions from Euphresco- and EPPO-related stakeholders and therefore is unsure whether it can be considered the result of a fully global consultation. He further raised his concern regarding whether the SRA should be

interpreted as feeding into, complementing, or running parallel to the IPPC's efforts in global research coordination.

Responding to this, Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) clarified that the situation is currently evolving. She explained that while IPPC is indeed exploring global research coordination within their own focus group, EIII's work represents a parallel initiative which is also being consulted by the IPPC. According to her, there is currently no formal mechanism ensuring how the SRA will be integrated into IPPC processes, and it remains unclear to what extent it will influence or align with IPPC outputs in the future. The SRA should therefore be understood as a contribution to the broader landscape rather than a formally embedded component within IPPC structures.

Ms. Donghia (CIHAEM-Bari, Int.) further developed this explanation by emphasizing that the SRA is explicitly intended to be complementary to IPPC rather than overlapping with it. She stressed that IPPC primarily focuses on regulatory frameworks and standard setting, whereas the SRA is concerned with research prioritization. From her perspective, there is therefore no structural conflict between the two, but the distinction could be articulated more clearly in the document itself.

Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) supported this interpretation and noted that, based on her understanding of recent IPPC activities, no fully operational global research coordination network has yet been established within IPPC. She underlined that this reinforces the idea that EIII's efforts are not competing with IPPC but rather contributing to an emerging space. However, she strongly emphasized that the IPPC Secretariat should be more actively involved in the process, particularly given the shared focus and the fact that IPPC is referenced multiple times in the document. She suggested contacting members within the aforementioned focus group and also offered her own help if needed.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) acknowledged that the Secretariat had been invited to participate in several feedback opportunities but confirmed that no input had yet been received. She agreed that a more targeted approach to engagement would be beneficial.

The discussion also included contributions from the Teams chat. In a Teams chat comment, Ms. Munaut (DG SANTE, Int.) questioned whether IPPC's networking activities are primarily focused on diagnostics. Ms. Anthoine clarified in response that IPPC currently runs two separate focus groups, one on diagnostics and another on research coordination, thus broadening the scope of IPPC involvement.

In a Teams chat comment, Mr. Jacobs explicitly supported the proposal to engage the IPPC Secretariat more directly, reinforcing the consensus that stronger interaction with IPPC is necessary.

Finally, Ms. Donghia emphasized that while engagement with IPPC is important, attention should also be given to the broader advisory board. She stressed that the SRA should not be shaped exclusively in response to IPPC but should reflect input from all advisory stakeholders involved in the project.

In response to this last comment, Ms. De Gottal noted that all Advisory Board members have been invited for the recurring feedback moments since the organization of the first webinar series. She thus emphasized the involvement of the Advisory Board has been, and will remain important for the development of the SRA.

Discussion summary: a shared conclusion emerged: while the SRA is broadly understood as complementary to IPPC, the relationship between the two remains insufficiently explicit and would benefit from both clearer articulation in the document and more direct engagement with IPPC representatives.

Session 2:

Mr. Nam (INRAE, FR) expressed uncertainty about who the document is designed for. He observed that the SRA appears to serve both the Euphresco-network and a broader global audience, but that this dual purpose is not clearly articulated. He suggested that the document should explicitly define its primary users and intended use.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) responded by explaining that the SRA is indeed intended to serve multiple purposes. Its primary function is to provide a basis for future network research calls, but it is also intended to act as a broader reference document that can inform and inspire plant health research beyond the network.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) reinforced this explanation, emphasizing that the SRA is a public document that can be used by external stakeholders, including countries and organizations not directly involved in EIII or the Euphresco-network.

Mr. Teulon (PFR, NZ) suggested that this dual purpose should be clearly stated at the beginning of the objectives within the document.

Discussion summary: there is still some uncertainty about who the SRA will be for. While it is intended to be used both by the future network coming out of the EIII-project, as well as outside of Euphresco, this dual purpose is not immediately clear and should be further elaborated on in the document.

1.5.2 Question 2: Do you think the SRA addresses the right level of ambition for global plant health research coordination?

Results summary: 88.0% of participants found the SRA to be appropriately ambitious, and 12.0% found it should be more ambitious.

Session 1:

No participants intervened verbally or via the chat.

Session 2:

In a Teams chat comment, Ms. McGaw (DAFF, AU) observed that the SRA successfully balances ambition with practicality. She noted that it addresses transnational coordination and innovation while remaining mindful of implementation constraints and emerging risks such as climate change.

Mr. Teulon (PFR, NZ) explained that although he had initially indicated a preference for greater ambition, he ultimately considers the current level appropriate given the uncertainties concerning the future governance of the network and the ongoing uncertainty regarding alignment with international organizations such as IPPC.

Discussion summary: the SRA is considered appropriately ambitious, especially concerning the current circumstances regarding the future network and relations to IPPC.

1.5.3 Question 3: Is it clear how the SRA relates to the IPPC framework, and that the SRA has been developed independently rather than as a direct reflection of the IPPC?

Results summary: 58.3% of participants find the relationship between the SRA and the IPPC clear within the document, 37.5% find it very clear, and 4.2% find it somewhat unclear.

Session 1:

Discussion summary: as this question overlapped substantially with the previous discussion, it did not generate additional input. Mr. Jacobs (DEFRA, UK) confirmed that his earlier concerns had already been addressed during the exchange on Question 1 and stated that he had no further comments to add.

Session 2:

Ms. McGaw (DAFF, AU) noted that while the relationship is generally clear, the independence of the SRA could be emphasized more strongly. She suggested clarifying how the two frameworks interact while remaining distinct.

Mr. Teulon (PFR, NZ) highlighted a more practical issue, noting that participants may find it difficult to assess this relationship if they are not familiar with the IPPC framework itself. He suggested that additional explanatory material, such as a link or brief description, could improve understanding.

Discussion summary: this discussion highlighted the same issues mentioned in session 1, being a need for a more elaborate distinction between the SRA and the activities of the IPPC. Furthermore, participants mentioned a reference to IPPC activities might be useful for those unfamiliar with this organization.

1.5.4 Question 4: The SRA is intended to cover medium-term (5-10 years) research priorities. How should the duration of the SRA be assessed and by whom? (open answers)¹

Session 1:

Mr. De Jonghe (ILVO, BE) introduced the idea that the duration of the SRA cannot be considered independently from the future structure of the network. He suggested that the organization of the future network, including its regional components, may influence both how duration is defined and how updates are managed, potentially leading to region-specific perspectives or requirements.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) agreed with this comment, stating the duration of the document will indeed depend on the future network structure. She added the current proposed duration is 7 years, mirroring the previous Euphresco-network SRA.

Building on this, Ms. Donghia (CIHAEM-Bari, Int.) proposed a concrete model combining a six-year overall duration with an intermediate consultation phase after three years. This would allow for iterative updates while maintaining a longer-term strategic framework. She further suggested that the responsibility for defining and reviewing the duration could lie with the GA or a similar governance body, although she emphasized that this remains to be discussed.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) acknowledged that the duration question is closely linked to the suggested evaluation process within the SRA draft. She suggested that a combination of fixed review intervals and more flexible, ad hoc updates could offer a balanced solution.

Ms. Nouwen added that doing a shorter-term consultation every 2 to 3 years would indeed be more appropriate than every 6 years. She also suggested extending the 6-year period to 7 years, including a 1-year revision phase.

Mr. Jacobs (DEFRA, UK) introduced an additional dimension by stressing the importance of incorporating an independent evaluation component into the assessment process. While he agreed that Euphresco members should play a central role, he suggested that an external or semi-independent mechanism would increase credibility and robustness.

In response, Ms. Nouwen confirmed that independent evaluations had been conducted in the past within the Euphresco-network and could be integrated again, potentially as part of a broader impact assessment framework.

Discussion summary: the exact duration of the SRA will depend heavily on the structure of the future network. There was broad agreement on the need for a structured yet flexible evaluation and adaptation approach, combining fixed cycles, interim reviews, and possibly independent evaluation mechanisms, while remaining adaptable to future governance arrangements.

Session 2:

Mr. Teulon (PFR, NZ) argued strongly in favor of regular updates, suggesting that the SRA should be revisited annually by the future network to allow rapid integration of new

¹ As this was an open-ended question, participants did not fill in a poll for this question.

developments. He emphasized that research priorities can shift quickly and that a static multi-year document may not be sufficiently responsive.

Ms. McGaw (DAFF, AU) highlighted the breadth of the question, stating it can refer to the overall duration of the SRA but also its update mechanisms. She suggested a long-term horizon of approximately ten years, combined with periodic untargeted evaluation cycles (for example every three to five years) and the possibility of annual targeted updates. In addition, she mentioned that once this evaluation process is more clearly defined, it should be implemented in the SRA with a detailed timeline. This way, readers know exactly in which phase of the cycle the SRA is situated and when they are able to provide feedback for the next update of the document.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) highlighted that these decisions are closely linked to the future operational model of the network. She also added that the suggested periodic evaluation could potentially link to new consultation rounds. Moreover, she introduced the idea of independent evaluations conducted at longer intervals, possibly as part of broader impact assessments.

Ms. McGaw responded that, from her perspective, the organization reviewing the SRA does not necessarily have to be external from the future Euphresco-network.

Ms. Nouwen further explained the evaluation process will have to undergo a transition phase as we progress towards the future network. Here, it will have to be decided how the document translates into real operations. The document should thus be considered subject to change. Mr. Teulon added this could also be reflected in the document with the addition of a disclaimer.

Discussion summary: participants agreed that the SRA should undergo regular updates and be treated as a dynamic document but acknowledged that the precise mechanisms for updating and evaluating it will depend on governance decisions that are still under development.

1.5.5 Question 5: How suitable and consistent did you find the terminology used throughout the draft SRA? (multiple answers could be selected)

Results summary: 48.5% and 33.3% of participants found the terminology used throughout the draft to be respectively very suitable and very consistent, 3.0% did not find it very suitable, 3.0% did not find it very consistent and 12.1% indicated 'other'.

Session 1:

Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) noted that while the terminology is appropriate, the repeated use of the term “objectives” at various levels of the framework leads to confusion. She pointed out that the same term is used for the cross-cutting considerations within the newly presented visual, as well as for more specific components within the draft, which may obscure the hierarchical structure. She suggested exploring alternative terminology to improve clarity.

In addition, Ms. Anthoine raised concerns about the use of the acronym “SRA” itself to refer to the Global Plant Health SRA within the document. She indicated that the distinction between the current document and previous SRAs is not always sufficiently clear because of this and suggested reconsidering the naming or explicitly differentiating between versions.

Reflecting on this comment, Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) asked whether SRA is the appropriate term to use here as the Global Plant Health SRA could be considered an update or a new version of the previous Euphresco SRA in a new context.

Ms. Anthoine responded it should be clearly stated within the document if the Global Plant Health SRA is an update of the previous SRA or if it is a completely new SRA. Especially for people not involved in the project or the Euphresco-network, this lack of clarity may lead to confusion.

Shifting the discussion, Mr. Jacobs (DEFRA, UK) confirmed that the definitions, particularly those distinguishing phytosanitary research from plant health research, are clear and consistent. However, he questioned whether the shift toward plant health terminology might

lead to an unintended expansion of scope. He expressed concern about potential “mission creep,” particularly when addressing new or non-regulated pests.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) responded by clarifying that the scope has not fundamentally changed. She explained that both regulated and non-regulated new and emerging pests were already included in the previous Euphresco-network SRA, but that the terminology has been updated to align more closely with IPPC definitions. The shift from “phytosanitary” to “plant health” terminology reflects this alignment, as well as the broader interpretation of the same scope considering the global context of the document.

Discussion summary: the exchange highlighted the importance of avoiding overlapping terminology, such as the word “objectives” within the visual, and the SRA-acronym, which is currently being used to refer both to the Global Plant Health SRA and the previous Euphresco-network SRA. Furthermore, the change in terminology towards “plant health” instead of “phytosanitary” was addressed, highlighting that it reflects a broader interpretation of the scope rather than a change in scope compared to the previous SRA.

Session 2:

Mr. Nam (INRAE, FR) raised concerns about specific terms, including “regulated pests,” noting that the authority responsible for regulation is not always clearly defined. Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) clarified that the term is based on IPPC definitions and therefore varies by region.

Mr. Teulon (PFR, NZ) suggested that glossary terms should be clearly marked in the text to guide readers, for example through quotation marks or other visual cues. He also recommended simplifying certain expressions, noting that qualifiers such as “strictly regulated” may be unnecessary and lead to confusion.

Mr. Nam also identified inconsistencies between definitions presented in the discussion slides and those included in the draft glossary, particularly regarding invasive alien species. Further into the discussion, Mr. Nam raised concerns about the use of the combined expression “new and emerging pests.” He explained that “new” and “emerging” pests represent distinct concepts, referring respectively to newly identified pests and to known pests that are expanding into new areas. He argued that merging these concepts into a single category could lead to conceptual ambiguity and proposed defining them separately or clearly using “new and/or emerging” to reflect their difference. Ms. De Gottal acknowledged that the glossary requires further refinement and alignment with the main text.

Discussion summary: terminology is generally considered suitable, but additional work is needed to ensure full consistency, clarity, and alignment across the document.

1.5.6 Question 6: To what extent does the current scope meet your expectations?

Results summary: 62.5% of participants found the scope of the SRA mostly meets their expectations and 37.5% said it fully met their expectations.

Session 1:

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) reiterated that the scope had undergone significant revision compared to earlier drafts, particularly in how it is framed within a global context. She emphasized that while the fundamental scope remains consistent with the previous SRA, its interpretation now encompasses a wider diversity of regional pest situations and research needs.

Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) responded by stating that the scope mostly meets her expectations, but she identified a structural issue in the document. She explained that key terms such as “ambitions” and “themes” are introduced early in the scope section without being defined at that point. This may create confusion, particularly for readers unfamiliar with the structure of the document.

Subsequently, Ms. Topitschnig (AGES, AT) provided a more elaborate reflection. She opened by commending the overall progress on the SRA and acknowledging that earlier feedback had clearly been considered. She remarked that the distinction between “plant health” and “phytosanitary” scope had improved in clarity and that the document is moving in the right direction. However, she raised a specific concern related to the globalization of the scope, namely the risk that stronger regional priorities, particularly those of Northern-Europe, might become diluted within a global framework. She stressed the importance of ensuring that regional needs can still be clearly prioritized and translated into research calls. In her view, additional clarification is needed regarding the operational process through which regional priorities are carried forward into future network calls.

In response, Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) acknowledged that this is indeed linked to how the future network will function operationally. She explained that the SRA itself provides a strategic framework, while the precise translation into research calls is determined at the

operational level of the network, for example through standard operating procedures. She agreed that this connection could be elaborated further.

Ms. Donghia (CIHAEM-Bari, Int.) complemented this by emphasizing that the consultation process already serves as the primary mechanism for capturing and representing regional priorities. According to her, the consultation results show that regions such as Europe North are well represented across objectives. She argued that the methodology ensures inclusiveness and that regional priorities are inherently embedded in the objectives derived from consultation results.

However, Ms. Topitschnig clarified that her concern was not whether regional priorities are present in the SRA, but rather how these priorities will be operationalized in the future network structure and call process. Ms. Donghia responded that it is still too early to fully define these mechanisms, as they depend on governance decisions that are yet to be finalized, especially concerning the structure of the future network and the modus operandi. She added the consultations and SRA are a means to define the methodology which will be used to identify research themes and topics in the future.

In a Teams chat comment, Mr. De Jonghe (ILVO, BE) expressed a similar concern, noting that he also perceived a lack of explicit regional focus, though he acknowledged that this is closely tied to the future governance model.

Discussion summary: while the scope itself is broadly accepted, further clarification is needed regarding the translation of global scope into regionally relevant actions, and that this is closely linked to future governance and operational decisions.

Session 2:

No participants intervened verbally or via the chat.

1.5.7 Question 7: Is the overall document consistently framed around this scope?

Results summary: 65.2% found the document to be very consistently framed around the scope, 30.4% found the framing consistent and 4.4% found it somewhat inconsistent.

Session 1:

No participants intervened verbally or via the chat.

Session 2:

Ms. McGaw (DAFF, AU) raised a specific concern regarding potential ambiguity in how certain objectives might be interpreted, particularly in relation to product development activities. She pointed out that some formulations could be read as extending into areas such as breeding or genetic work, which, from her perspective, are commercial activities and therefore fall outside the intended scope of the SRA.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) responded by clarifying that the scope section explicitly excludes purely commercial product development. However, she acknowledged that this distinction may not be sufficiently reflected within individual objectives and agreed that further clarification could be necessary to avoid misinterpretation.

Mr. Teulon (PFR, NZ) offered a complementary perspective, noting that the boundary between research and product development can be context-dependent and difficult to define in practice. He provided the example of breeding work carried out in response to a plant health crisis, which, although it may result in commercial outputs, is driven by urgent phytosanitary needs and conducted within research organisations. This example illustrated that excluding such activities entirely could risk overlooking important areas of plant health research.

In response to this exchange, Ms. De Gottal acknowledged the complexity of distinguishing between these categories and agreed that the wording could be adapted to better reflect this nuance.

Discussion summary: while the overall structure is perceived as consistent, certain elements of the scope still require careful framing throughout the rest of the document to accommodate different interpretations across regions and disciplines.

1.5.8 Question 8: Which of the following subjects do you feel should be considered and/ or explicitly stated within the scope of the SRA? (multiple answers can be selected)

Results summary: 50.0% of participants feel phytosanitary or plant health treatments should be considered and/ or explicitly stated within the scope of the SRA, 33.3% feel invasive alien species should be included, 8.3% think pesticides should be included, 2.8% think none of these subjects should be included and 5.6% voted for ‘other’.

Session 1:

Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) explained that she selected the “other” option because the relevance of these topics does not lie in their inclusion as standalone categories, but rather in their role within integrated plant health solutions. She further elaborated that projects addressing only one of these aspects would be less relevant and emphasized that effective plant health strategies rely on combining multiple methods, including pesticides, treatments, and other control measures, rather than focusing on any single component in isolation.

Ms. Donghia (CIHAEM-Bari, Int.) supported this position, noting that it is neither realistic nor desirable to exclude pesticides or treatments entirely from the scope. She stressed that their relevance depends on context and should be understood within a broader integrated pest management framework.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) recognized that this could be incorporated into the scope by clarifying that such elements are included when they are directly related to plant health objectives and integrated approaches.

Discussion summary: subjects such as pesticides and plant health treatments cannot be excluded completely from the SRA as they form important components of integrated management approaches. According to participants, this should be better reflected within the document.

Session 2:

Ms. McGaw (DAFF, AU) reiterated her earlier concern regarding pesticides, emphasizing that while they are an important component of plant health strategies, their inclusion in the scope must be carefully framed to exclude product development. She stressed that research on pesticides should focus on their role within integrated management approaches rather than on the development of new commercial products.

Mr. Teulon (PFR, NZ) introduced a different line of reasoning, questioning whether explicitly listing such topics within the scope is necessary at all. He argued that the scope could become overly complex if it attempts to enumerate specific subjects, particularly when these are already implicitly covered within broader definitions and subsequently elaborated within the objectives. In his view, maintaining a high-level scope would improve clarity and prevent redundancy.

His argument was supported by Ms. McGaw, who acknowledged that adding further definitions or categories at the scope level could create confusion rather than clarity. She suggested that detailed thematic coverage might be more appropriately addressed within the objectives of the document. In a Teams chat comment, Ms. Day (CFIA, CA) also explicitly indicated agreement with Mr. Teulon's position, reinforcing the sentiment that the scope should remain general rather than exhaustive.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) acknowledged the validity of this observation and agreed the scope should remain broad. Mr. Teulon suggested adding a statement to the scope section to clarify the objectives illustrated within the Research Themes further outline the scope.

Discussion summary: general agreement that the scope section should remain broad but should indicate the objectives within the document provide further clarification on what can be considered within the scope of the SRA.

1.5.9 Question 9: How appropriate do you find the current set of objectives in the SRA? (multiple answers can be selected)

Results summary: 57.1% of participants agreed the objectives are well structured as they are while 23.8% voted for some objectives to be removed, 4.8% thought some objectives should be merged, 4.8% found some objectives should be split, and 9.5% voted for ‘other’.

Session 1:

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) kicked off the discussion by presenting a potential new structure for the objectives, which had been suggested by the team of Mr. Hietala (NIBIO, NO) as part of their written feedback on the current draft. This new structure especially focuses on merging some objectives across the different Research Themes and Ambitions.

Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) stated her preference for maintaining detailed objectives, arguing that they are essential for practical implementation, particularly when linking research proposals to specific objectives. She warned that overly broad objectives could complicate evaluation processes and reduce clarity when assessing whether a project aligns with the SRA. At the same time, she expressed reservations about certain Ambitions, which she considered too general rather than having concrete objectives. She suggested that these may instead be better reflected as a framework within the document rather than being framed as objectives.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) reflected on this last comment by mentioning certain projects from previous calls may only fit under objectives currently linked to the Ambitions.

Ms. Anthoine responded, saying she finds some of the Ambitions very relevant, but others not as much. Following up on this discussion, she asked whether a “stress test” of the objectives had been conducted yet by mapping recent project calls to the current structure to assess the practical relevance of each objective. Ms. De Gottal acknowledged that such a stress test was planned but had not yet been conducted.

Mr. De Jonghe (ILVO, BE) linked the discussion to the indicator tools being developed under WP3 of the EIII-project and contributed by highlighting the importance of flexibility. He described the SRA as a “living document” that must be adaptable to evolving research needs. He also noted that no matter how detailed the objective structure is, there will always be cases where projects do not neatly fit into predefined categories.

Mr. Hietala expressed concern that some objectives appear artificially split, using the example of two objectives related to diagnostics (T1.1 and T1.2) that seemed to overlap significantly. He suggested that excessive splitting could create confusion for readers and lead to unnecessary complexity, recommending that related objectives be merged where appropriate.

Ms. Donghia (CIHAEM-Bari, Int.) shared her point of view, being that she felt the distinction between these example objectives was quite clear. She liked the fact that we differentiated potential research topics under the same theme.

Ms. De Gottal and Ms. Nouwen responded by explaining that the existing distinctions within the objectives are often based on differences in research purpose, even where there is technical overlap. However, they acknowledged that these distinctions may not always be sufficiently clear and agreed that further refinement could be beneficial.

Discussion summary: some objectives, especially beneath the Ambitions, may be less relevant and that these could be identified via a stress test. Participants concluded this discussion with some opposing stances concerning the structure of the objectives. While some prefer the detailed separation of objectives, others feel these distinctions are somewhat artificial. Although the discussion did not generate a conclusive decision, the goal will be to balance detailed objectives while avoiding over-fragmentation.

Session 2:

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) introduced the topic by recalling an alternative structure that had been proposed by Mr. Hietala. She invited participants to reflect on whether the current level of granularity is appropriate.

Most participants did not express concerns, and a Teams chat contribution from Mr. Nam (INRAE, FR) explicitly noted that the current version represents a significant improvement compared to earlier drafts. Ms. McGaw (DAFF, AU) also added in the Teams chat that she likes the current structure, with the added suggestion of changing the wording of IPM ‘development’ to IPM ‘implementation’.

Mr. Aveskamp (NVWA, NL) provided a more detailed evaluation, indicating that while the overall structure is strong, certain objectives could benefit from refinement. He specifically pointed to objectives T1.1 and T1.2, suggesting that they could either be split further or restructured to better reflect the diversity of techniques they encompass. In his view, the current formulation combines too many distinct elements, which may reduce clarity for readers. He also suggested that one particular objective related to circular bioeconomy (A2.4) might fall outside the core focus of the SRA and could be reconsidered for removal.

Ms. De Gottal acknowledged that the latter is a concern which had been raised by multiple participants and explained that the decision to include all identified objectives was based on a desire to reflect all consultation outcomes. At the same time, she recognized that objectives with limited support or relevance may naturally diminish in importance over time and agreed

to revisit their positioning. To address Mr. Aveskamp's concern on cluttered objectives and themes, Ms. De Gottal agreed to re-evaluate the current structure of the objectives.

On a different note, Mr. Teulon (PFR, NZ) questioned how the plant health scope, including new and emerging pests, can be linked to sustainable pest management within the objectives. He asked if this meant only new and emerging pests could be considered for sustainable pest management or if long-standing pests should also be included. Ms. McGaw clarified in the Teams chat that these pests are usually new and emerging somewhere, thus suggesting the process is implied but could be more clearly described.

Discussion summary: while the structure of the objectives is broadly accepted and considered a large improvement from the previous draft, continued refinement is still needed here and there to avoid cluttered Research Themes and objectives. In addition, some slight tweaks were suggested for objectives concerning IPM and sustainable pest management.

1.5.10 Question 10: Is it clear how objectives under Research Themes and Ambitions are expected to translate into future Euphresco research calls?

Results summary: 78.3% of participants found the way objectives under Research Themes and Ambitions are expected to translate into future Euphresco calls to be clear, 8.7% agreed it was very clear, 8.7% said it was somewhat unclear, and 4.3% selected ‘other’.

Session 1:

No participants intervened verbally or via the chat.

Session 2:

No participants intervened verbally or via the chat.

1.5.11 Question 11: Underneath each objective, the Champions whose inputs were used to establish that objective are listed. How should these references to the “support” of objectives be handled in the SRA?

Results summary: 54.6% of participants felt the current approach (“...based on input from the Champion(s) for:...”) should be kept, 22.7% agreed the references to “support should be removed entirely, 13.6% felt explicit support should be collected from Champions and/ or individual organizations to be implemented in the final SRA, and 9.1% selected ‘other’.

Session 1:

Mr. Hietala (NIBIO, NO) suggested that the usefulness of listing supporting regions or organizations depends on whether there are meaningful differences between objectives. If all objectives are broadly supported by similar stakeholders, this information may be redundant; however, if certain objectives have more specific or limited support, then indicating this could be valuable for readers.

In response, Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) clarified that there are indeed significant differences among the objectives. While most are broadly supported, other objectives are very specific to certain regions and/ or disciplines.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) added that this system of expressing which regions and disciplines support a certain objective was adopted from the previous Euphresco-network SRA, albeit slightly adapted to the global context of the current document.

Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) proposed replacing the current textual references with a more visual representation, such as a table included in an annex. She suggested that such a table could map regions or disciplines against themes and objectives, allowing readers to easily identify patterns of support without relying on repetitive textual statements.

Mr. De Jonghe (ILVO, BE) showed support for Ms. Anthoine’s suggestion but also raised a more fundamental concern, noting that attributing support to specific Champions could imply unequal influence among members of the EIII-project.

Clarifying the thought process behind the current approach, Ms. Nouwen stated it was a response to previous feedback, which felt support could not be expressed for a whole region or discipline without consulting all organizations within. Thus, the current draft refers to support being expressed by the individual Champions who represent those regions/ disciplines, although she agrees this might also not be the most appropriate wording.

Ms. Donghia (CIHAEM-Bari, Int.) supported moving away from references to individual Champions and instead focusing on the fact inputs came from the regional consultations, thus better reflecting the collective nature of the input.

Discussion summary: it was agreed that a more visual representation of support, combined with a focus on the consultation process as opposed to individual Champions or regions and disciplines, would likely be more appropriate.

Session 2:

Mr. Teulon (PFR, NZ) expressed reservations about the current approach, noting that attributing objectives to Champions or specific contributors could be misleading. He explained that the process of developing objectives involves interpretation and synthesis of consultation inputs rather than direct endorsement, and that this nuance is not adequately captured by the current wording. He suggested that terms such as “input” would more accurately reflect the process.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) confirmed that the intention behind including such references was to illustrate the extent of support for each objective, particularly in terms of distinguishing between globally supported and region/discipline-specific priorities. However, she acknowledged that the current textual approach may not be the most effective way to convey this information. Drawing on feedback from the previous session, she proposed replacing textual references with a more visual format, such as a table or annex, that would map consultation inputs across regions and objectives.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) supported this idea, emphasizing that the consultation process, rather than individual Champions, should be the primary reference point. She noted that attributing support to Champions may inadvertently misrepresent the broader consultation results.

Mr. Nam (INRAE, FR) added that the term “Champion” itself may be problematic for readers unfamiliar with the project’s internal terminology and suggested avoiding it in favor of more neutral language.

Discussion summary: the current approach should be revised, with strong support for replacing textual attribution with a visual and consultation-based representation that more accurately reflects the collective nature of the input.

1.5.12 Question 12: Which objectives do you link to which cross-cutting considerations?

Participants were asked to submit their answers to this question via e-mail (by contacting Samantha De Gottal directly) using the table provided at the end of the questionnaire which was sent alongside the official invitation for the webinars. Any such contributions will be carefully reviewed and used to refine the next draft of the SRA. We have already developed an initial internal proposal for how these links could be interpreted, which you can find in the slides (slide 96) sent along with this report. This can serve as a basis for your answer but please feel free to send in your own interpretations as well.

No submissions have been received for this question yet, but they are still welcome at samantha.degottal@health.fgov.be.

1.6 Future Development of the SRA – Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) proceeded with the final presentation and formal closing of the webinar. She began by expressing her appreciation to all participants for their active engagement throughout the sessions, to those who had submitted written feedback in advance, as well as to participants who had contributed during the General Assembly. She emphasized that the feedback received during the discussions was highly valuable for the ongoing development of the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA).

Turning to the projected timeline for the SRA, Ms. De Gottal provided an overview of the next steps in the development process. She explained that the project is currently situated at a stage of finalization. In the coming period, the project team will focus on further refining SRA 2.0, integrating the feedback obtained during both sessions of the webinar series. Looking ahead, she outlined that the next major milestone is expected to take place during a planned physical GA, tentatively scheduled for October. Here, an (almost) final SRA will be presented.

Following the GA, Ms. De Gottal explained that additional feedback opportunities would be organized to support the finalization process. These opportunities are expected to take various forms, potentially including bilateral discussions or other targeted consultation methods, although the exact format had not yet been fully defined. She stressed that these additional feedback rounds will be essential for refining the nearly final version of the document and ensuring that it adequately reflects the perspectives of all relevant stakeholders. She concluded by clarifying the ultimate objective of the process, which is to produce a fully finalized SRA that can be formally presented and, ideally, endorsed at the conclusion of the EIII-project.

Ms. De Gottal then shifted the focus to what she described as the “unfinished business” required to reach this final stage. She identified four main areas requiring further work. First, she emphasized the need to integrate the most recent feedback collected during the webinar sessions. Second, she noted that further refinement of the glossary and the consistent use of definitions throughout the document remain necessary, acknowledging that terminology still requires improvement in terms of clarity and alignment. Third, she highlighted the intention to reintegrate the presented visual into the SRA in a more functional way. Rather than simply serving as an illustrative addition, this visual should actively support the reader’s understanding of the document’s structure and content. She indicated that this work is being undertaken in collaboration with a graphic designer within FPS Health. Finally, she referred to the need for a thorough review and improvement of the overall writing quality to ensure the document reaches a high level of clarity and coherence.

As part of these final refinements, Ms. De Gottal introduced a proposal to establish a small editorial group composed of native English speakers. The purpose of this group would be to assist in polishing the final version of the document, focusing particularly on language, style, and readability. She invited interested participants to volunteer for this role and encouraged them to contact her via email.

In closing, Ms. De Gottal reiterated her gratitude to all participants for their time and contributions. The sessions ended with final expressions of thanks exchanged between participants, marking the conclusion of the webinar.